

According to [Budimir Drakulic PHD](#), the electrophysiological study is a test that is useful for the diagnosis of patients who have or may have alterations in the heart rhythm (arrhythmias). It allows to know the type and severity of the arrhythmias, the place of the heart where they originate and the disorders that it produces. It also serves to better focus the treatment that should be applied to such arrhythmias if they exist.

What is the electrophysiological study?

The heart is a muscle that drives blood through a system of vessels (arteries and veins). The heart valves are responsible for directing blood in the proper direction. In addition, the heart has an electrical system, which is responsible for issuing the necessary impulses to mark the heart rate and adapt it to the needs of the body. As Budimir Drakulic PHD explains, the alterations of the electrical system of the heart produce alterations of the rhythm or arrhythmias. There are slow arrhythmias or bradycardia when the rhythm of the heart slows down and rapid arrhythmias or tachycardias, when the rhythm becomes faster. The electrophysiological study diagnoses them and guides them on their treatment.

How is the electrophysiological study performed?

For the performance of the electrophysiological study it is necessary that the patient is fasting.

The subject must undress and lie down on a special stretcher in the electrophysiology laboratory. Generally, the technique is usually performed after administration of sedation to the patient.

Local anesthesia is applied to the puncture site (veins and / or arteries of the groin, arm or neck) so that the puncture is not painful, and catheters (thin, long and flexible cables) are introduced that go to the heart through X-ray (radioscopy) or other type of location systems that do not require radiation and are known as non-fluoroscopic navigation system (such as Navex © system, CARTO ©, Rhythmia © among others).

[In his studies](#), Budimir Drakulic PHD points out the catheters serve to permanently record the electrical activity of the heart from within, define the type of arrhythmia and where it is located. The electrical activity is shown on monitors. Catheters can also serve as a pacemaker if an external stimulator is connected.

Sometimes it is necessary to administer a drug during the test to determine the diagnosis of the arrhythmia. At other times, an electric shock will be required. To do this, the patient is anesthetized.

The procedure has a variable duration, being able to last between 30 minutes and several hours.

When finished, the patient has to remain at rest for several hours to avoid complications in the puncture site.

What are the risks of this test?

According to Budimir Drakulic PHD [research publications](#), although the technique is indicated properly and is performed correctly, undesirable effects may occur:

Mild

It is common for the patient to feel palpitations during many moments of the study, as they are caused by the catheters or by the effect of the medication administered. Sometimes it is necessary to apply an electric shock to solve a sudden problem. In most patients there will be only slight discomfort in the puncture site or the appearance of a hematoma that will almost always be spontaneously reabsorbed.

Serious

There are rare complications such as phlebitis, venous or arterial thrombosis, hemorrhages in which a transfusion is necessary. Cardiac perforation with cardiac tamponade, pulmonary or systemic embolism is very rare. These are serious complications that require urgent action. Being an invasive procedure, it has a mortality rate, although it is a very infrequent complication (1 patient out of every 3,000 in which the study is performed).